

COMPARISON OF THE RESULTS IN THE STUDY OF ATMOSPHERIC AIR POLLUTION WITH DUST

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Abstract

An air pollutant is any gas or particle that, in high enough concentrations, can seriously harm human health and the environment.

As a result of observations by several researchers, environmental pollutants have been studied. It can be seen that it leads to global warming and depletion of the ozone layer.

Pollutants in atmospheric air (PEMs) remain one of the most important issues for human health worldwide. The rapid development of many branches of industry, the increase in the speed of traffic, has a negative impact on the urban ecosystem. It is necessary to organize monitoring of atmospheric air pollution by dust at all permanent points of the city.

Abstract

In heated air, there are gases and particles, which in sufficiently high concentrations can cause serious harm to human health and the environment.

And as a result, the environment of the environment is illuminated by researchers in the satellite line. Vidno, chto eto privodit k globalnomumu popleniyu i stoshcheniyu ozone layer.

Atmospheric air pollution (PEM) remains one of the most important problems for human health and the world. Burnoe razvitie mnogix otrasley promyshlennosti, uvelichenie skorosti dviganiya transporta negativ skazyvaetsya na gorodskoy ecosekistome. It is necessary to organize monitoring of atmospheric air pollution and all stationary points in the garden.

Annotation

Air pollutants are any gases or particles that, in sufficiently high concentrations, can cause serious harm to human health and the environment.

As a result of the observations of a number of researchers, environmental pollutants were studied. It can be seen that this leads to global warming and depletion of the ozone layer.

Outdoor air pollutants (PEM) remain one of the most important human health problems worldwide. The rapid development of many industries, the increase in the speed of transport has a negative impact on the urban ecosystem. It is necessary to organize monitoring of atmospheric air pollution by dust in all stationary points of the city.

Keywords: In the atmosphere, substances, gas, human qi pollutant in concentration, environment, anoat, motor vehicles, urban ecosystem, human health, diseases, sanitary hygiene laboratory, organic compounds nitrogen oxides, increase of industry, development, movement, development showing a secret.

Keywords: Atmosphere, veshchestvo, gas, concentration zagryaznitelya si humaneka, okrujayushchaya sreda, anokat, motor transport, urban ecosystem, norm, zdorove humaneka, disease, sanitary-hygienic laboratory, organic soedineniya, okidy azota, rost promyshlennosti, razvitie, dvigennie, vozdeystvie. shows

Keywords: Atmosphere, substance, gas, human qi pollutant concentration, environment, anokat, vehicles, urban ecosystem, norm, human health, diseases, sanitary laboratory, organic compounds, nitrogen oxides, industrial growth, development, movement, impact. shows.

- Currently, continuous monitoring of atmospheric air pollution by the Hydrometeorological Service Center (Uzgidromet) in the Republic of Uzbekistan is carried out at 65 permanent points in 25 cities. Including, in the city of Andijan, monitoring of atmospheric air pollution is carried out at 4 permanent points. On the days of the clean air month, the highways of the regional districts will also be monitored.

1- post. Motorway.

2- post. Babur and Gagarin streets.

3- post. Residential district (Mashrabi Street)

4- post. Industrial enterprise (Yu. Otabekov Street).

It makes an important contribution to research-level learning in the monitoring of 10 air pollutants at fixed points. As a result of the scientific research conducted by Hyun Mi Cho, Jongke Lee, they determined the chemical pollutants, i.e. carbon monoxide and dioxide, formaldehyde, volatile organic compounds, nitrogen oxides, by studying the atmospheric air quality factors. The average value of air quality is as follows - less than 12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{less}$, the average level of carbon dioxide - 754.2 ppm, formaldehyde - 46.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, volatile organic compounds - 335.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2$, the total number of bacteria in the air amount - 37.8 SFU m^2 and radon - 59.5 Bq/ m^2 . He believes that continuous measurement is necessary for accurate analysis of air quality [1]. The profit or loss of each substance is determined according to the permitted amount. Even the chemicals in the products we use in our lives and the foods we eat can become poison if they exceed the norm. Substances that do not decompose in a natural way, and have a negative effect when combined with each other in excess of a certain amount, are considered dangerous for human health [2]. As most people age, the amount of chemicals consumed exceeds the permissible level. Sometimes, toxic substances in consumer goods increase the strength of each other and have a negative effect on the body. As a result, diseases occur. Later, the process of all-round development, as a result of providing various comforts to humanity, caused natural inconveniences around it. As a result of the rapid growth of the urbanization process on earth, new cities are emerging. [3]. The total area of cities in the world is 0.5 mln. sq. km. is 0.3% of the Earth's surface. 49 percent of the world's population lives in cities with more than 100,000 inhabitants. Urban population is 74% of the entire population in North America, 71% in Europe, 86% in Great Britain [4]. In Uzbekistan, it is 25%. The conducted research has shown that substances extremely dangerous for human health, mainly vehicles emit carbon dioxide, exhaust gas, and various other compounds that are harmful to human health. The total area of cities in the world is 0.5 mln. sq. km. is 0.3% of the Earth's surface. 49 percent of the world's population lives in cities with more than 100,000 inhabitants. Urban population is 74% of the entire population in North America, 71% in Europe, 86% in Great Britain [5]. In Uzbekistan, it is 25%. The conducted research has shown that substances extremely dangerous for human health, mainly vehicles emit carbon

dioxide, exhaust gas, and various other compounds that are harmful to human health. The total area of cities in the world is 0.5 mln. sq. km. is 0.3% of the Earth's surface. 49 percent of the world's population lives in cities with more than 100,000 inhabitants. Urban population is 74% of the entire population in North America, 71% in Europe, 86% in Great Britain [6,7]. In Uzbekistan, it is 25%. The conducted research has shown that substances extremely dangerous for human health, mainly vehicles emit carbon dioxide, exhaust gas, and various other compounds that are harmful to human health. Urban population is 74% of the entire population in North America, 71% in Europe, 86% in Great Britain [8,9]. In Uzbekistan, it is 25%. The conducted research has shown that substances extremely dangerous for human health, mainly vehicles emit carbon dioxide, exhaust gas, and various other compounds that are harmful to human health. Urban population is 74% of the entire population in North America, 71% in Europe, 86% in Great Britain [10,11]. In Uzbekistan, it is 25%. The conducted research has shown that substances extremely dangerous for human health, mainly vehicles emit carbon dioxide, exhaust gas, and various other compounds that are harmful to human health.

Pollutants in atmospheric air (PEMs) are one of the most important issues for human health on a global scale [12,13]. Pollutant pollution levels are high in developed countries, and airborne pollutants are detected [14,15]. The main source of atmospheric air pollution is motor transport and accounts for about 70% of atmospheric pollution. In addition, small particles emitted from motor vehicles, including rubber particles emitted from the car body, are dangerous for breathing and life in general (as a result of the breakdown of a single car, 10 kg of dusty rubber particles are mixed into the atmosphere in a year [16]. Hydrometeorology according to the information provided by the service center, Almalyk and Fergana, as well as Navoi and Kokan cities are among the cities with the most polluted air in terms of air pollution by harmful substances. In Uzbekistan, the waste released into the atmosphere from permanent (stationary) sources has reached 1.3 million tons. Sulfur dioxide amounted to 538,800 tons, hydrocarbons to 427,000 tons, nitrogen oxides to 94,100 tons and solid pests to 317,400 tons. Determination of harmful substances in atmospheric air, including dust, sulfur dioxide, nitrogen dioxide, formaldehyde,

In the example of the city of Andijan, one of the major industrial cities of our republic, for the purpose of monitoring the pollutants and small volatile particles emitted by motor vehicles into the air of the city, four street areas of the highway, i.e. A. Temur, Babur, Navoi, Cholpon shah ko researches were carried out in Alisher Navoi Park as a control option.

The rapid development of many branches of industry, the increase in the speed of traffic, has a negative impact on the urban ecosystem.

During 2017, air samples were taken and chemical analyzes were carried out in order to determine the amount of harmful factors in spring, summer and autumn. When the tests were analyzed in laboratory conditions, the results of the experiments carried out in the spring, summer and autumn months of 2017 show that dust 0.27 mg/m³, sulfur 0.067 mg/m³, nitrogen anhydride 0.36 mg/m³, formaldehyde 0.062 mg/m³, lead 0.0011 mg/m³ amounted to Nitrogen oxides 2.2 ml/m³ formaldehyde 2.1 ml/m³ lead 1.8 ml/m³ were found to be more than the permissible amount [1.3.1– is a reference in the figure].

Fig. 1. Results of the analytical analysis carried out in the research objects

According to the conclusion of the table, the results of the analytical analysis of the research objects show that in 2017, according to the data of the DSENM of the Andijan region, mainly dust T-1, T2 (Table 1.3.1) shows 0.4 percent, sulfur 0.1 percent, nitrogen 2.2-2.4 percent, formaldehyde 2.2-08 percent, lead T-1 percent, T- And 2 was 0.2-03 percent, and the state of dust and substances in the atmosphere was shown.

As can be seen from the table, the above-mentioned dust and other substances are low compared to the permissible norm [table 1.3.1- is a reference].

Table 1

The results of the tests taken from the main streets of Andijan city

Experien ce points	Dust	Sulfur	Nitrous anhydride	Formaldehy de	Lead
N-1	0.27 mg/m3	0.067 mg/m3	0.36 mg/m3	0.062 mg/m3	0.0011 mg/m3
N-2	0.14 mg/m3	0.086 mg/m3	0.33 mg/m3	0.064 mg/m3	0.0013 mg/m3
Fixed rate	0.5 mg/m3	0.5 mg/m3	0.085 mg/m3	0.035 mg/m3	0.0015 mg/m3

Clean and pure air and as clean a natural environment as possible are indicated as the main condition for a healthy lifestyle. The cleanliness of the environment depends on the amount of substances present in it. In other words, if the amount of a chemical is higher or

lower than normal, it will cause harm. If the amount of dust in the atmosphere exceeds the permissible limit, it causes respiratory and allergic diseases. The data confirmed by the Andijan Regional Health Department for 2018-2019 show that circulatory system diseases from 14991 to 16949, asthma from 320 to 359, congenital anomalies from 417 to 460, appeared in the perinatal period. Some cases have increased from 3339 to 4867. In our experiments, the total amount of pollutants emitted from motor vehicles is 18-20 percent. Due to these harmful substances, diseases have increased by 1.5 times in the cities of Uzbekistan, and bronchial asthma has increased by 20%. It was observed that the children's ability to fight against infectious diseases decreased by 25 percent.

Physical, chemical and biological mechanisms are used to control and prevent air pollution from various sources.

In development processes, power generation, incineration, chemical and metallurgical industries, agricultural chemical formulation, asphalt and cement production and other stationary sources, as well as biomass burning and agricultural operations and mobile sources (gasoline, including sources such as jet fuel, etc [17,18]. Global warming related to climate change is currently one of the most discussed topics. There are natural causes as well as various anthropogenic effects that lead to atmospheric air pollution around the world.

In 2005-2006, monitoring of atmospheric air pollution by dust in the city of Tashkent was carried out in 5 out of 13 permanent points (2, 4, 6, 15, 28 permanent points), in 2007-2011 in 4 out of 13 permanent points (2, 4, 6, 15, -constant points) were carried out [19,20].

Observations showed that in 2005, the average annual amount of dust released into the atmosphere at point 4 was 0.3925 mg/m³, which is higher than the daily average permissible concentration (REKsutka.or=0.15 mg/m³) was high. In the remaining 4 permanent points, the level of dust pollution did not exceed the REK. In 2005, the lowest average annual indicator of pollution level (0.0643 mg/m³) was observed at point 15.

Atmospheric air pollution with dust was observed to be higher than REK in point 4 in 2006, that is, the average annual amount of dust was 0.3142 mg/m³. Also, in 2006, the level of pollution was higher in comparison to 2005 at point 2 located near the territory of the enterprise "Tashkent Agricultural Machinery". In 2006, the level of dust pollution was the lowest in point 28, that is, the average annual amount was 0.0767 mg/m³. In general, it can be noted that in 2006, air pollution of Tashkent city with dust was higher than in 2005. In 2007, no sample was taken from the dust released into the atmosphere at point 4. In the remaining 3 permanent points, the level of dust pollution did not exceed the REK.

Atmospheric air pollution with dust The average annual amount of dust released into the atmosphere at point 4 in 2008 was 0.1625 mg/m³, exceeding the daily average permissible concentration (REKsutka.or=0.15 mg/m³) was high. In the remaining 3 permanent points, the level of dust pollution did not exceed the REK.

In 2009, the level of dust pollution in 4 permanent points did not exceed REK.

Atmospheric air pollution with dust The average annual amount of dust released into the atmosphere at point 4 in 2010 was 0.2708 mg/m³, exceeding the daily average permissible concentration (REKsutka.or=0.15 mg/m³) was high. It can be considered that the high level of dust in the air at this observation point is caused by the pollution released into the air from the "Tassisiksuvcenterkaz" and the abrasive combine located near this point. In the remaining 3 permanent points, the level of dust pollution did not exceed the REK.

Atmospheric air pollution of the city of Tashkent in 2011, the average annual amount of dust released into the atmosphere at point 15 was 0.1627 mg/m³, exceeding the daily average permissible concentration (REKsutka.or=0.15 mg/m³) was high.

In the remaining 3 permanent points, the level of dust pollution did not exceed the REK.

It is necessary to improve the efficiency of the existing treatment facilities at the "Tashissiksuvmarkaz" enterprise, which is one of the largest facilities located near point 4, and to replace the equipment with modern ones. The city of Tashkent should organize monitoring of air pollution by dust at all permanent points.

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